

Analysis of Gender Inequality Indian Women’s faced on Workplace

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Abstract— Gender based discriminations is a universal fact especially in case of poor or lower class women’s. We speak only men and women both are equals to each other but in reality it’s not fact. Gender discrimination mostly based on stereotypes concept makes by society. In today era peoples are educated but their thinking is backward based, they consider men are physically and mentally strong rather than the women’s. They thought women are physically weak and emotionally sensitive. Gender discrimination term comes from the conflicting with the term sex. In my opinion both terms are used to be as equality or synonyms to each other but technically too much difference between the both terms. In simple words we can say that gender discrimination means that the men and women are not equal to each other. Mostly these difference is comes from the distinctions in biology, psychology, and cultural norms etc. Studies show the gender equality between them of many domains like education, life experience, personality, interests, family life, careers and physical structures extra too much factors influences on the term of Sex. In India, a number of industries are stratified across the genders .These difference is main reason behind this according to me family, location and society their we lives. Because some time lower-class families are uneducated, so they are not encourage own their children’s for study specially girl child ,they think what’s benefit to teach the girl child ,after marriage girl child only done the household work .They were not favor of educated the girl child’s. But some time middle class or little educated family provides equal chance to their child’s for studies but girls are not give more preference to their careers as compared to their families Because they choose any jobs to considers some points like timing of job, working hours, location, on the work place which type of works assigns them? And atmosphere of Workplace etc. The reason behind this a single women’s play a very vital role in her life like as a mother, as a wife and in a company as a employees. She will always manage her personal life or professional life whether she is educated or illiterate. In this paper we study about what’s Gender equality or Discriminations facing by the women’s in workplace.

Keywords— Female Labor participation, Gender Inequality, Income differences, Women Inequality Law.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gender discrimination shows the inequality difference between the men and women. It’s based on physically and mentally potential of individuals. Men and women working capabilities are different to each other. Women have performed work in same capacity. The main reason of discrimination is lack of knowledge about women rights. The

employer may not discriminate the employees on the basis of sex, religion and color. Gender discriminations most affected the life of girls and women throughout their life. Mostly discrimination facing by girls and women’s are often ones of that suffering from poverty. Women performed the task efficiently on work place as compare to men. But women are not take initiative towards own rights. So women are less weighted as compares to men’s. On the workplace less educated men’s appointed on rather than the women. Some time does the work under the supervision of women hurt the ego of men?. Today era standard of living is so much high so women’s also contribute financially to their families because to manage children’s education, Health problems too much reasons and circumstances arises in the family So need to women’s for doing the job. A gender bias creates at the workplace. Women’s workers in India faced many problems and challenges during the job. In India mostly women’s do household work like house cleaning, cooking washing cloths and care of children etc ,but men not give any contribution in house hold works.

II. FEMALE LABOR PARTICIPATION IN INDIA

Today era is a competitive world. To fulfill the basics needs like food, shelter, and clothes. Except the basic needs to provide the good educations to children’s, to handle health problems and others factors influence the life. Money is a key of to fulfill the all requirements of life so women’s are also contribute to the family as a financially. Women’s came out the home may be they are educated or may not be. To survive the life and provides to their children’s to better life .They are doing the jobs. On the workplaces women’s suffering from many problems and challenges. So below we discuss about all problems and challenges one by one. In India women’s workers participation shown in Figure 1 and 2.

India: Women in the Workforce

✓ Not willing to work	44
✓ In labor Force	27
✓ Willing to work	24
	05

✓ Others	100
Total female labor	

India: Women In The Workforce

Source- : 5 key lessons about women and work in India (Rediff.com business)

In India, a number of industries are stratified across the genders. But some time middle class or little educated family provides equal chance to their child’s for studies but girls are not give more preference to their careers as compared to their families Because they choose any jobs to considers some points like timing of job, working hours, location, on the work place which type of works assigns them. In indian female worker’s participation shown in Figure 3.

Female Labour Force Participation (%)

Source: ILO via World Bank, Government of India Ministry of Labour and Employment

Source-: Why Indian workplaces are losing women’s

In India Gender Inequality concept taking a huge shape. In comparison of women’s get the less wages . It’s a global problems is deeply roots in India shown in Figure 4.

SOURCE: THE GLOBAL GENDER GAP REPORT 2017, WORLD ECONOMIC FORUM

III. THE SITUATION WOMEN OF INDIA

In Indian society, women are not treated equally, if any decision taking about itself career and about children not allowed them. In India the huge quantity of work women must to do only a routine household work like cleaning of houses, cooking, looking the kids and to be support their families, working women’s only limited rights they get.

From the beginning when they are born in family, young Indian girls are the victims of favoritism. Mostly boys provide higher education, nuterician food over the girl’s ratio. This gender inequality is also present in education, ownership of properties distributed by parents among sons rather than girls. Girls to do support their mothers in household work and forced girls to do work and looking younger brother and sisters to help their families. For many Indian women, poor dealing, violent behavior and mistreatment take place on daily basis..

Indian societies do indeed be familiar with many women’s rights, including the rights, family support and set up a business. However, in rural areas, poverty and a lack of information represent real barrier to women’s liberty and empowerment. Programs aimed at advance human rights, literacy are therefore necessary in order to protect Indian women to the place they deserve and open doors to better future opportunities.

IV. PROBLEM FACED BY WORKING WOMEN’S ON WORKPLACE

A gender bias creates at the workplace. Women’s workers in India faced many problems and challenges during the job. In India mostly women’s do household work like house cleaning, cooking washing cloths and care of children etc ,but men not give any contribution in household works. Except the basic needs to provide the good educations to children’s, to handle health problems and others factors influence the life.

Women preference only that jobs , easily maintain the personal and their professional life. As result women’s missing from workplace shown in Figure 5.

MISSING WOMEN

Source: World Development Indicators

Money is a key of to fulfill the all requirements of life so women’s are also contribute to the family as a financially. Women’s came out the home may be they are educated or may not be. To survive the life and provides to their children’s to better life. They are doing the jobs. On the workplaces women’s suffering from many problems and challenges. So below we discuss about all problems and challenges one by one.

- Mental Harassment**
- Sexual Harassment**
- Discrimination at workplace**
- Lack of safety women’s at travelling time**
- Lack of Family Support**
- Insufficient maternity leaves**
- Job security**
- Workplace adjustment**
- Working hours**
- Unequal pay**
- Insecurity**

- **Mental Harassment-** On the workplace a women faced the too much stress because every working woman alone manage the household work and workplace work. She maintains the balance between her personal life and professional life but an employer can’t understand her problem, an employer only demand and expectation from there the good work. So women’s are fully stressful and mentally upset.
- **Sexual Harassment-** Some Time by the employers feels the women’s uncomfortable on the workplace under the law it’s a crime. An employer does the

unethical behavior with them. Women’s always should be to take strictly step against the employers.

- **Discrimination at workplace** – In modern era men thinks they are more caliber to performed the tasks rather then women’s but this statement is not true as like a men’s ,women’s also doing the task efficiently and effectively but by employers underestimate their performance.
- **Lack of safety women’s at travelling time** – Women’s not only faced the problem within the organization ,same challenges and problems daily faced during the travelling from home to workplace duration.
- **Lack of Family Support-** Women’s give her hundred percent to financially contribution but sometimes women’s caliber underestimate by their family members. Willingly family members not support them.
- **Insufficient maternity leaves-** We are human beings suffering from health problems in case of women’s when they want to leave regarding maternity but employers not willingly provide the leaves.
- **Job security-** As compare to men’s, women’s performance no count. Employers think women’s are not physically strong as compare to men’s So men also had more opportunities of higher salary, promotions etc benefits provides the men’s.
- **Workplace adjustment-** Always women’s are doing the compromise and adjustment in life. They are known, gender discrimination arises on the workplace, Unequal pay but they are not strictly step against the employers.
- **Working hours-** A single women plays a many role in our life as like a mother, as like a wife and as an employee or working women but her duties not off whole life. So working hours not in her favor but she compromise.
- **Unequal pay-** Today is modern era but on the workplace women’s are not equally treated by employers. Unequal pay, unethical behavior suffering by women’s on workplace.
- **Insecurity** – Sometime unhealthy environment provides by the employers so women’s are not fully secure but to fulfill the basics needs they doing the job in this unethical environment.

V.TYPES OF GENDER INEQUALITY

Gender inequality is a global problem to unfair treat the individuals based on their gender. Gender Inequality roots are so deep and affected the Indian economy.

- Inequality in Family
- Natality Inequality
- Professional in equality

- Ownership Inequality
- Household Inequality
- Special opportunity Inequality

VI. REASONS FOR GENDER DISCRIMINATION ON WORK PLACE

Sex and gender both are different in origin but physically role of individuals must have to be used his/ her mentally thinking in order to move in the society. Gender discrimination means on the workplace different ways to be used to treat a men and women powers. About the women's our backward thinking is women's are weak physically and mentally. They are emotionally based take the all decisions. Women's are not mentally strong as compare to men's to take efficiently decisions. Reasons of gender discrimination shown in below Figure 3.

Reasons for Gender Discrimination on Work Place

- ❖ **Poverty**
- ❖ **Lack of monetary sources**
- ❖ **Lack of Knowledge about women's rights**
- ❖ **Social customs, beliefs and norms**
- ❖ **Lack of education**
- ❖ **Lack of trade unions in favors of women's**
- ❖ **Lack of awareness of women's**

Poverty- Poverty is a main reason behind the gender discrimination because every person's needs money to survive the life so women's also needs to do a job so anything offers by employers they accepted not refuse their proposals so discrimination arises.

Lack of monetary sources –Money is a basic need and motivational factors in our life. To fulfill the basics needs women's are agree to doing a job for the support of our family members. Lack of money sources they work as employees on the workplace.

Lack of Knowledge about women's rights – Women's are lack of knowledge about women's Act and what are the rights of women's .So that reasons gender discrimination arises.

Social customs, beliefs and norms – In our society rules, customs and norms are against the women's freedom. Our society think women's are weak, not to do any work without permission of men and family members.

Lack of education - Lack of education arises the gender discrimination. Women are work on the workplace without any bargaining about the unequal pay system.

Lack of awareness of women's – Women's are totally unaware about the women's rights. They never take the initiatives for own benefits.

Lack of trade unions in favors of women's – Trade union play a very vital role for employees welfare, trade union on the behalf of employees represent their demands in front of

Employers but specially not take the decisions in favor of female workers.

VII. WOMEN CONSTITUTION IN INDIA

In India Everybody Person right to choose the profession. But gender discrimination is a global problem in whole world unequal treatment individuals on the basis of gender is deeply rooted problems in India. Every person free for choosing the profession on own choices in safe surroundings. Today era women's also come out from their comfort zone and doing the work because of family needs, for the children better futures. But in India Not equal treat the men and women's. On the workplace women's not treat as a human being. Gender Discrimination at work Discrimination is defined political belief, religion, sex, social beginning or national extraction, etc, which has the effect of nullifying or impairing equal) of prospect and treatment in employment or occupation.

VIII.STATUS OF WOMEN IN INDIA

Equal rights are every person freedom like women with respect to status, opportunity, protection of law with respect to a social, economic and political issue in accordance to the foreword. Now era women's not equally treat because of gender reason. Rural India has the highest record for mortality during childbirth. Hours spent in household activities by women are ignored by the Census. Women payment of daily wages when compared with men.

IX .EXISTING LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK

Specific aspects of women equality are mentioned in the Constitutional laws but anti-discrimination code is missing. An example of civil law which addresses any violence in domestic sector is mentioned in the Protection of Domestic Violence Act, 2005. There is no broad statutory definition of inequity that takes into account special manifestations of prejudice and its blow in the deficiency of an anti- discrimination code. The National Human Rights Commission and the National Commission for Women are constituted to safeguard and protect human rights. These Commissions have their limitations too. Individual grievances are not being entertained here neither the Commission can bind a government's decision regarding the issues.

X. CONCLUSION

Today era standard of living is so much high so women's also contribute financially to their families because to manage children's education, Health problems too much reasons and circumstances arises in the family So need to women's for doing the job. A gender bias creates at the workplace. Women's workers in India faced many problems and challenges during the job. In India mostly women's do household work like house cleaning, cooking washing cloths and care of children etc ,but men not give any contribution in household works. Gender discrimination shows the inequality difference between the men and women. It's based on physically and mentally potential of individuals. Men and women working capabilities are different to each other. Women have performed work in same

capacity. The main reason of discrimination is lack of knowledge about women rights. The employer may not discriminate the employees on the basis of sex, religion and color.

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